

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the relevance of the digital transformation process in Language Education in Uzbekistan. The impact of digital technologies on the language learning process, existing problems and prospects are considered. Also, problems such as infrastructure preventing the development of digital language education in Uzbekistan, digital literacy of teachers, shortage of electronic resources are covered in detail. The article also analyzes public programs, international cooperation and the role of the private sector. At the end, proposals and recommendations were made to accelerate the digital transformation of language education.*

Keywords: *language education, digital transformation, online education, technologies, Uzbekistan, digital literacy, educational innovation, electronic resources.*

ЦИФРОВАЯ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ В ЯЗЫКОВОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируется актуальность процесса цифровой трансформации языкового образования в Узбекистане. Рассматривается влияние цифровых технологий на процесс изучения языка, существующие проблемы и перспективы. Также подробно освещаются такие проблемы, как инфраструктура, препятствующая развитию цифрового языкового образования в Узбекистане, цифровая грамотность учителей, нехватка электронных ресурсов. В статье также анализируются государственные программы, международное сотрудничество и роль частного сектора. В завершение были высказаны предложения и рекомендации по ускорению цифровой трансформации языкового образования.*

Ключевые слова: *языковое образование, цифровая трансформация, онлайн-образование, технологии, Узбекистан, цифровая грамотность, образовательные инновации, электронные ресурсы.*

Introduction. The rapid globalization trends of the 21st century have forced organizations, including educational institutions, to make significant changes to digital transformation.

According to the OECD digital economy perspective, digital transformation affects economies and societies in a complex and interdependent manner, which requires sustainable strategic approaches (OECD, 2020).

Organizations are increasingly adopting digital technologies such as cloud computing, big data, and artificial intelligence to maintain their relevance in a constantly evolving market (Omar, 2020). Digital transformation is a decisive factor in the success of business and educational institutions, providing opportunities for improving efficiency, improving customer experience and innovation (Mushtaha, 2022). Digital transformation is important to OTMs because of its ability to meet the evolving demands and expectations of students in the digital age. Students now expect continuous digital experience, personalized learning, and access to digital resources (Abad-Segura, 2020). By adopting digital transformation, institutions can increase student engagement, improve educational outcomes, and increase overall satisfaction. In addition, digital transformation allows institutions to simplify administrative processes, increase operational efficiency and reduce costs.

Through the implementation of digital systems, the automation of tasks and the use of data analysis (Nadkarni, 2021), institutions can optimize their activities, make decisions based on data information and distribute resources more efficiently than ever (Benavides, 2020).

Main part. In the modern world, digital technologies are entering all aspects of our lives.

The field of education is no exception. In particular, language education processes are also developing under the influence of digital transformation. In Uzbekistan, the use of digital technologies in the study and teaching of foreign languages is important. This article will analyze the processes of digital transformation in Language Education in Uzbekistan, the problems faced and the available opportunities.

The introduction of digital technologies in Language Education provides the following advantages:

- 1.The quality of teaching increases – Multimedia textbooks, interactive games and virtual laboratories make language learning more interesting and effective.
- 2.Flexibility and convenience – with online platforms and mobile applications, students will have the opportunity to learn a language anywhere and at the right time.
- 3.Individual approach-programs that work on the basis of artificial intelligence can analyze the level of knowledge of each student and offer suitable exercises for him.
- 4.A wide range of resources – open databases, e-books and interactive textbooks on the Internet will further enrich the language learning process.
- 5.Global integration-through online courses and international cooperation programs, students will have access to foreign educational resources.

Digital transformation is a process that combines digital technology with business strategy in every possible way, facilitating change in the fields of technology, culture and operations, business processes and human resources to create new business models and encourage innovation

for business to continue. This requires organizations to reinvent themselves and modify all processes using digital technology to respond to changing markets at appropriate intervals.

Digital transformation is very important for companies that want to be competitive in today's rapidly growing business landscape. It helps organizations streamline processes, improve customer experience, achieve their strategic goals, and means integration into all areas of the organization. When it comes to functional operations, digital transformation can simplify processes, increase efficiency, and improve customer experience.

There are a number of problems in converting language education to digital format in Uzbekistan. They can be classified as follows:

1. Infrastructure problems

- Most schools and higher education institutions lack modern computer technology.
- The quality and speed of the Internet is insufficient in some regions.
- There is not enough technical support for the use of digital tools in educational institutions.

2. Digital literacy of teachers

- Many teachers do not have sufficient qualifications in the use of digital technology.
- Courses for teaching digital educational methodologies for teachers are not sufficiently organized.

3. Shortage of quality electronic resources

- There are not enough quality online resources, video tutorials and interactive materials suitable for national curricula.

- There are few artificial intelligence systems and automated training programs that work in the Uzbek language for learning foreign languages.

Results and Discussions. At the same time, Uzbekistan has certain opportunities for the development of digital technologies in language education:

1. State support

- The government of Uzbekistan is implementing a number of programs for digitizing the education system.

- The "e-learning" system is being developed and many e-textbooks are being created.

- The focus on digital education is growing through presidential schools and IT parks.

2. International cooperation and projects

- Uzbekistan cooperates with international organizations and foreign universities, mastering advanced experience in the field of digital education.

- Online courses and opportunities for international certificates are expanding.

3. Private sector participation

- Private initiatives aimed at creating digital education platforms, online training courses and interactive textbooks are growing in Uzbekistan.

-Mobile applications and web platforms for language training are being developed by IT companies.

4. Increased demand and motivation

- There is an increasing interest in learning foreign languages among young people.

- Due to the prevalence of Internet and mobile technologies, there is a high demand for digital education.

These opportunities will help accelerate the digital transformation of language education.

In Uzbekistan, the process of digital transformation in language education is carried out in stages. However, there are problems that need to be solved in this area. It is important to develop infrastructure, train teachers in digital literacy and create quality electronic resources. At the same time, this process can be accelerated by strengthening public, private sector and international cooperation.

In conclusion, it can be said that the process of digital transformation is important in Language Education in Uzbekistan, and modern technologies make the educational process more efficient, convenient and interactive. Through digital education, students and students will have the opportunity to learn foreign languages anywhere and at the time. At the same time, it is possible to strengthen the individual approach using artificial intelligence, mobile applications and online platforms.

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